
PROBLEM ASSOCIATED WITH TRANSLATION OF G. ORWELL'S INDIVIDUAL FEATURES

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Annotation: The aim of the article is the individual stylistic features of the language of George Orwell's journalistic works and the possibility of their preservation in translation into Uzbek.

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Analyzing the translation of Orwell's essays, we sometimes encountered the fact that the author's text "sounds" differently than its Uzbek version and, in our opinion, is perceived differently by the Russian-speaking reader than it should be perceived in the original language; in other words, the functional equivalence of linguistic means is not achieved, which is the main criterion for the adequacy of translation (Retsker Ya.I., 1974: 9). There can be many reasons for this: violation of the rhythm of the text; a significant lengthening of the sentence, "weighting" it; change in the stylistic coloring of individual words or phrases; as well as various kinds of inaccuracies. Trying to identify the causes that caused these phenomena, we first of all remembered the "literalism" problem, which, to one degree or another, was touched upon in their works by almost all translation theorists in our country.

"Literalism" should not be equated with literal translation. Many prominent translation theorists have spoken in favor of the latter, often interpreting the concept of "literal translation" in their own way. So, A. Malblanc in the book "Comparative stylistics of the French and German languages" "classifies this type of translation as a "direct translation" along with borrowing and tracing paper." (Malblanc A., 1961: 26-27.).

L.L. Nelyubin and G.T. Khukhuni characterize literal translation as "aspiring to preserve the formal and semantic components of the original when transferring it to another language..." and note that this type I translation, along with close to it verbatim translation, was widely used in the history of translation to convey texts of various genres." (Nelyubin L.L., Khukhuni G.T., 2001: 6.)

At the same time, I.A. Kashkin, a prominent translator and translation studies theorist, believed that "literal translation, conveying words, not speech, language, and

not words, cannot fully convey the text, a work of fiction.” Kunin, in his turn, made an attempt to classify literalisms, highlighting lexical and grammatical literalisms. Literalism in translation can, without distorting the meaning of the text, make it sound "not quite in Uzbek", and in this case one can speak of a practically adequate translation. In the course of this study, we considered the transmission of negatively colored vocabulary in Uzbek versions of G. Orwell's essays, especially noting cases where the presence of literalism in the translation did not allow preserving negativity, and those where excessive verbatim did not prevent the reproduction of a sharp, sometimes offensive coloring. Perhaps the greatest difficulty in translating vocabulary with negative and offensive connotations in journalistic works of G.Orwell is caused by the transfer of various nicknames. Analyzing various manifestations of literalism, we once again became convinced that it is far from always possible to even approximately define a specific example as "lexical" or "grammatical" literalism, not to mention a more detailed classification. The author of this definition K.I. Chukovsky bitterly noted: “in our literature, a special, conditional, translation language has been developed, which has nothing in common with the genuine language.” (Chukovsky K.I., 1936: 67).

This capacious definition includes various manifestations of literalism and many other phenomena that negatively affect the quality of the translated text. For example, excessive passion for foreign words. It seems to us that the problem of excessive enthusiasm for transcription in translation is closely related to literalism; often these phenomena have common causes, for example, "difficulties with the selection of the Russian equivalent or wording of the phrase, inaccurate assessment of the individual stylistic features of the translated author, too long work with the text, when the translator ceases to distinguish what sounds "foreign", and what - no, etc. Another aspect of "translating language" that is directly related to literalism. The issue of using an inappropriate meaning of the polysemantic seems to us much more subtle than the classical “literalisms”, and it is much more difficult to explain what shortcomings, in our opinion, the given examples contain, but in this study we could not help touching on this topic. As practice shows, even the most experienced translators can sometimes allow elementary literalism, using the wrong meaning of a polysemantic word.

In this case, we are talking more about literature that affects sensations - the feelings of the reader, but has nothing to do with sensations. As for the phrases, later in the text of the essay "The Suppression of Literature" it is said that the English newspapers are full of advertisements inviting those who wish to literary workshops, where, for a moderate fee, they will be provided with ready-made plots plus the opening and closing phrase of each chapter. Thus, creativity in literature has often been reduced to a minimum, and the next stage, according to G. Orwell, is writing

books without human participation at all. Thus, the translation of the highlighted passage could be: "Perhaps some low-grade love fiction / romance novels will survive - they will be churned out in a streaming method, reducing the participation of a person to a minimum." (Translated by F.O.)

An inaccurate choice of the meaning of a polysemantic word, as in the examples above, can disrupt the sound of an entire sentence or an entire paragraph. As the wonderful translator K.Chukovsky, "... the art of a translator, in its highest achievements, consists in merging with the will of the author. The translator should not take on translations of those authors who, by their temperament and by the nature of their talent, are alien or hostile to him." (Chukovsky K., 1936:56). Unfortunately, it is not always possible to follow the advice of the master. Excessive liberty, like literalism, greatly harms the quality of the translation. Comparing the text of the original and the Uzbek version, you are once again convinced that the quality of the translation is negatively affected by differences in the individual styles of the foreign author and translator. We should note that the unmotivated softening of the author's expressions is harmful to of G. Orwell's works and their translation, since he used to call a spade a spade, neglecting euphemisms.

Literalism in the translation of the underlined words consists, in our opinion, in the preservation of the English vowel "ai" in the Uzbek analogue of the underlined word, as well as in the absence of compensation when rendering this word - after all, in Russian it is hardly possible to pronounce the word "face" incorrectly, even when a completely uneducated person. And the liberty of this translation lies in the arbitrary "transplantation" of the English vowel into the Russian word. It seems to us that when translating an example, lexical replacement is simply necessary, especially since "the translator is free to use any compensation suitable - phonetic, morphological, syntactic means." Compensation for English vernacular could be made by using Uzbek non-literary forms such as "semi-clinic", "sausage", "kofe" instead of "coffee". The last option seems to us the most successful of those proposed, since this word also exists in English, and has a similar sound, so the compensation is not even noticeable in the translation. In addition, it is unlikely that the addition of a complete one contributes to a more accurate transfer of the author's thought.

“The problem of the negative influence of the original language on translation is extremely complex and multifaceted, and hardly even the most talented and experienced translator is able to constantly follow the requirement of K.Chukovsky to think all the time in native language, and only in native, not for a moment succumbing to the influence of foreign turns of speech that are alien to the syntactic laws of the native language.” (Chukovsky K.I., 1936: 65)

It seems to us that often people who are fluent in a foreign language and have been working with it for a long time become so accustomed to grammatical constructions, phraseological turns and other features of a foreign language that, without noticing this, they transfer them into speech in their native language. Therefore, the reason for the emergence of a "translation language" can be precisely the high professionalism of the translator, as well as ordinary physical fatigue from long work with a foreign text, which causes addiction to foreign language constructions. But, since this work is devoted to the analysis of the translation of Orwell's works, we could not help but dwell on what can greatly degrade the quality of translation. Analyzing the unsuccessful, in our opinion, moments in the translations of the essay of a talented English publicist into Russian and offering our own version, we always remembered that it is always easier to follow the beaten path and, moreover, such an analysis cannot but be subjective.

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